

Tool 8

Assemble the project team

Welcome to the Citizen Science Starter Kit.

This template is part of Module 4 “Getting started with citizen science” (phase 1 – Prepare), which helps you to assemble your project team.

Please download this template to your own folder and fill it in on your local computer. If you have any further questions about this template, please contact citizenscience@vub.be.

Use this template by Muki Haklay¹ below to consider the most prominent members of your citizen science project, and fill out who you have in mind for each role. Notice that, again depending on the size of the project, multiple roles might be fulfilled by the same person.

Role	Description	Responsible
Project manager	Coordinates between scientists, developers, community members, and other organizations that are involved in the project, ensuring that the project progresses as expected.	Marc
Scientist	Provides the scientific support to the project and help in designing the methodology, ensuring that information is of good quality.	
Community manager	Manages the communication with participants, promotes the project on various social media, and provides updates through such channels.	
Science communicator	Prepares the scientific information that will be shared with participants and answers questions in a language that is accessible to a wider public audience.	
Community scientist	Provides training to participants to ensure that the methodology is well understood and that the information in data sheets, apps, and website(s) is understood by participants. The community scientist can also help in	

¹ Muki Haklay, Citizen Science and Policy: A European Perspective. Washington, DC: Woodrow Wilson International Center for Scholars, 2015.

	framing the local problem as a research question that will be integrated into the project.	
Software developer	Supports the development of apps and web-based data collection systems. Develops the main project website, linking it with various social media, email lists, etc.	
Data manager	Maintains the information that is provided by participants. Uses appropriate procedures to ensure the quality of the information. Ensures that the data is protected and shared appropriately.	
User interaction and experience specialist	Ensures that apps, websites, and data collection forms are easy and enjoyable to use and assists in evaluating the levels of engagement in various media and the usability of digital tools.	
Graphic and information designer	Ensures that the project information is presented in a consistent way across printed and digital media, and provides advice on information visualization.	
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